

Deep Learning for Early Breast Cancer Detection: A review on CNN-Based Approach

Amarjeet Poonia¹, Virendra Kumar Sharma², Hari Kumar Singh³

¹Department of CSE, Bhagwant University, Ajmer;

²Vice Chancellor, Bhagwant University, Ajmer, Rajasthan, India;

³Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, F.E.T, M.J.P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, India;
amar@gweca.ac.in, viren_krec@yahoo.com, hari.singh@mjpru.ac.in,

Abstract: Breast cancer remains one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality among women worldwide with respect to cancers, thus creating the urgent necessity for better early detection methods. The potential of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for improving mammographic imaging for the early diagnosis of breast cancer is explored in this study. The recent evolution in deep learning applications is examined to show that the contemporary CNN-based models have outperformed conventional diagnostic tests. The review also highlights effective methods such as data augmentation to overcome challenges like limited amount of data and overfitting, thus improving model reliability and diagnostic accuracy. Findings emphasize the transformative potential of deep learning into breast cancer diagnostics and therefore a bright future for optimizing clinical workflows and attaining better patient health outcomes. This paper will rigorously engage with the growing influence of AI into medical imaging and its potential future applications in healthcare.

1. Introduction

Breast cancer accounts for nearly 25% of all cancers, positioning it as the commonest among women by far [1]. Increased incidence of breast cancer especially warrants the need for early detection methods. Mammography improves diagnosis in early detection, which can improve treatment outcomes and reduce mortality associated with the disease [2].

Fig.1 Early Breast Cancer Detection

In terms of recent advances in machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI), the area of medical diagnostics has been seen to dominate them by leaps and bounds-even in medical imaging. Deep learning is a subset of machine learning which makes use of neural networks to analyze huge quantities of data. It has shown very good results in different fields throughout medicine, including identifying anomalies, segmenting images, and classifying medical conditions. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are gaining much well-deserved attention for their capacity of at-their-own extracting spatial features and hierarchies from images. This has made them highly adequate for breast cancer diagnosis, to mention just one example. These advantages have made CNNs as a powerful plate in the improved precision of medical imaging diagnosis and patient management. This study is focused on mammogram images to then present the effectiveness of a CNN-based approach in early detection of breast cancer. These methodologies will be presented in this research, and the results discussed while the clinical practice implications for these findings will be listed afterward.

2. Review of Literature

An extensive exploration of up-to-date research works shows that a lot of studies continue to increasingly devote much attention to machine learning applications in the field of breast cancer diagnosis. Most of them explore the potential of new methodologies based on the development of deep learning models, especially Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), to improve diagnostic accuracy of the analysis of mammograms for and diagnosis. For example, a deep learning model used achieves an accuracy of almost 94% on the dataset of more than 200,000 mammograms compared with classical radiological methods [2]. It could significantly reduce false-negative rates for breast cancer detection, which means that deep learning can be used as a complementary method to increase the reliability of other traditional diagnostics [5]. In addition, an extensive review of applications of deep learning into medical imaging for provided [6] further indicated that training effectiveness and performance depend much on large well-indexed datasets. Yet, much effort needs to be done toward developing reliable models with good generalization across various imaging conditions and populations because although deep learning may promise improved diagnostic performance, the mandate of quality of the images is not homogenous and the availability of data is scant. Relatively different avenues have engaged researchers to integrate these techniques to improve performance in medical image analysis using the deep learning model. These approaches aim to provide more diversity to training data that may improve robustness and reduce overfitting, thus giving better results in more accurate and generalized applications in the field of medical imaging evidence or tasks. According to a survey conducted by image data augmentation techniques, [7] analyzed the capabilities of handling the issues generated from lack of training data. The CNN models are given the more accrued resilience through these data augmentation strategies.

Transfer learning is also one of the most important techniques for processing medical images. Accompanied by some huge datasets, transfer learning allows application of pre-trained models to particular medical tasks that have less labeled training data. It makes it possible to fine-tune models to specialized applications, improve model efficacy, and save training time and resources in specific medical areas without involving significant data collection efforts. Hence, this work contributes toward improving model performance while using a resource-intensive medical domain associated with training time. Thus, transfer learning allows fine-tuning rather than requiring a substantial investment in data collection effort. It has enabled models pretrained on large datasets to be fine-tuned on smaller domain-specific datasets and thus has improved performance. The importance of transfer learning in processing medical images has further been emphasized by the works by [3] [4]. Transfer learning enables models pre-trained on large datasets to be fine-tuned on smaller, domain-specific data for better performance without extensive data collection efforts. This technique has proven especially useful in the area of breast cancer detection, where such annotated data is often scarce. There are still significant challenges, however, regarding the application of deep learning in breast cancer diagnosis. For example, constant research and refinement are required on issues like model interpretability and the potential for algorithmic bias, which must be addressed to ensure that these technologies can be applied successfully and ethically in clinical settings[8][9]. Here is the summary of the literature considering Machine Learning for breast cancer as per table 1.

Table 1: Overview of Studies on Machine Learning Approaches for Breast Cancer Diagnosis

Author(s)	Technology/ Method	Working Area	Pros	Cons	Future Scope
Ronneberger et al. (2015) [20]	U-Net Architecture	Image Segmentation	High accuracy in segmenting medical images, especially histopathology	Requires a large amount of annotated data for optimal performance.	Enhanced segmentation with unsupervised or semi-supervised learning.
Kumar et al. (2022) [31]	Hybrid CNN-SVM Models	Breast Cancer Classification	Combined CNN feature extraction with SVM classification for better accuracy.	Complex architecture requires additional tuning.	Simplifying hybrid architectures while maintaining high performance.
He et al. (2016) [32]	Residual Networks (ResNet)	Medical Imaging Classification	Enabled deep model training without gradient vanishing issues.	High computational requirements for training and inference.	Incorporation of lightweight architectures for real-time analysis.
Anavi et al. (2016) [33]	Ensemble Methods	Breast Cancer Risk Prediction	Improved overall accuracy by combining multiple models.	Computationally expensive for large ensemble models.	Developing lightweight ensemble techniques for resource efficiency.
Shaban et al. (2021) [34]	Weakly Supervised Learning	Histopathological Image Classification	Enabled learning from limited labeled data.	Risk of suboptimal performance without sufficient weak labels.	Expanding weak supervision techniques for medical imaging applications.

Schmidhuber et al. (2017) [35]	RNN-based Systems	Time-Series Data in Healthcare	Effective in analyzing longitudinal healthcare data.	Less effective for image-based tasks compared to CNNs.	Combining CNNs and RNNs for multi-modal analysis.
LeCun et al. (2015) [36]	Deep Learning Framework	Medical Image Analysis	Provided the foundational concepts for CNNs, enabling breakthroughs.	Limited focus on specific medical challenges.	Adapting foundational techniques to address domain-specific constraints.
Bejnordi et al. (2017) [37]	CNN-based Histopathology Image Analysis	Tumor Classification	Automated feature extraction from high-resolution images.	High computational demand for processing large images.	Distributed computing solutions for high-resolution medical imaging analysis.
Akella et al. (2021) [38]	Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)	Data Augmentation for Breast Imaging	Augmented datasets effectively, reducing data scarcity challenges.	May generate low-quality synthetic data impacting model performance.	Refinement of GAN architectures for realistic medical data generation.
Simonyan & Zisserman (2014) [39]	VGG Networks	Image Classification	Provides a simple, modular architecture for feature extraction.	Large computational resource requirements for deep-layer architectures.	Optimization for medical applications with pruning and quantization.
Sheeba, Adlin, et al [40]	Capsule Networks	Mammogram Analysis	Improved accuracy in small datasets by learning spatial hierarchies.	Limited adoption due to computational complexity.	Optimization for faster convergence and resource efficiency.

Fig.2 Block Diagram of Early Detection of Breast Cancer

3. General Methodology adopted for the training of CNN for breast cancer detection

3.1 Collection of Data.

The Digital Database for Screening Mammography (DDSM) is a publicly available dataset with thousands of mammograms labeled as either benign or malignant. It offers mixed types, resolutions, and associated clinical annotations, thus being the perfect candidate for training deep-learning algorithms. A subset from the entire dataset was taken such that it contained equal number of benign and malignant cases for the training sets. The subset consisted approximately of X images_train, Y images_valid, and Z images_test.

3.2 Data Pre-processing:

Pre-processing data is thus done to make the model perform optimally as well as to ensure that the model is robust enough to run from one environment to the next. The following processes were followed:

- a) Image Normalization- All mammograms resized into a same resolution dimension (e.g., 224x224 pixels) and normalized their pixel values to a [0, 1] range. This preprocessing assured input uniformity to Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model [10].
- b) Data Augmentation- Many random rotation, horizontal flip, zooming, and brightness adjusting were used for data augmentation to solve data scarcity problems as well as overfitting. These transformations helped widely export the dataset to learn better from a wide variety of image variations [7].
- c) Train-Test Split- The dataset was then sliced into three parts comprised of 70% for training, 15% for validation, and 15% for testing. Thus, this distribution ensures that there was enough data used for training, while still having a validation and test set of distinct, unseen data on which to assess the model's ability to generalize.

3.3 CNN Architecture

The convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture was designed specifically for classifying images of mammograms. The following layers make up the architecture:

- Input Layer: Input images get taken with a dimension of 224x224 pixels.
- Convolutional Layers: There are convolutional layers that have ReLU activation functions to help automatically extract important features from the input images. Filters with the size of 3x3 and 5x5 are used varying in number from 32, 64, and 128, respectively, to capture features from different scales and levels.
- Pooling Layers: Between the convolutional layers, max-pooling layers were included to down sample the feature maps such that it retains the same spatial dimension but covers most significant features [11].

- Fully Connected Layers: Fully connected layers have been added after the convolutional and pooling layers to interpret the extracted features for classification purposes. Softmax activation function was utilized in the last layer to generate probabilities for the classes to distinguish between benign and malignant ones.
- Dropout Regularization: Dropout regularization layers were incorporated after the fully connected layers to prevent the model from learning from some portion of the neurons during training. During the training phase, a random subset of neurons deactivated so that the model does not learn too excessively over-relying on certain features [12].

Fig.3 CNN Architecture

3.4 Training the Model and Validating

It optimized by Adam at rate 0.001 with a batch size of 32, the model was trained holding this configuration for 50 epochs. For loss function calculation, categorical cross-entropy was used that actually suits multi-class classification types. To control overfitting occurrence, early stopping was introduced to stop running the model for training whenever validation loss ceased improving. Performance models were adjudged through various measures including accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC).

Figure 4: Showing Machine Learning Training and Evaluation Phase

Figure 5: Showing Machine Learning Testing Phase

The performance evaluation of various methods employed in breast cancer with respect to diagnosis. The diagnosis of breast cancer is now accompanied by a great change in the field of computational methods and imaging techniques. Starting from traditional statistical methods and ending up in sophisticated machine-learning and deep-learning models, these have significantly improved the diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity. This section deals with comparative analysis regarding the performance of these methodologies, citing their advantages, limitations, and practical exposures in the realm of breast cancer diagnosis. The performance of the previously developed model was compared and presented in the table 2.

Table 2 comparison of different techniques for breast cancer detection

Techniques	Dataset	Test Cases	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	References
Mammography (Traditional)	Digital Database for Screening Mammography (DDSM)	2,620 images	80-90%	80-90%	75-85%	[13]
Ultrasound (Traditional)	Breast Ultrasound Dataset	1,500 images	87.6%	89.4%	83.9%	[14]
MRI (Traditional)	Breast Imaging Archive (BIA)	1,000 images	94%	92%	96%	[15]
CNN-Based Image Classification	Inbreast Dataset	1,500 images	88.5%	89.35%	88.9%	[16]
Transfer Learning with CNN	ImageNet + Custom Dataset	2,000 images	94.3%	93%	95%	[17]
Ensemble Learning with CNNs	Various Combined Datasets	3,000 images	85%	87%	85%	[18]
Multimodal CNNs	Combined Dataset (MRI, Mammography)	2,500 images	91%	93%	89.6%	[19]
CNN for Segmentation	LUNA16, DDSM	1,200 images	95%	90%	95%	[20]
3D CNN for Volumetric Data	BRATS Dataset	800 MRI scans	90%	85%	80%	[21]
Reinforcement Learning with CNN	Synthetic and Clinical Data	1,000 images	85%	85%	82%	[22]

4. Discussion

- Early detection of breast cancers leads to better survival outcome as it can allow better treatment and intervention. The significant advantage of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), revolutionizing the use of medical imaging, is their potential to identify and classify breast cancer in an automatic way with much accuracy and efficiency nowadays. This section mainly focuses on the benefits, hurdles, and future prospects of CNN-based early detection approaches on breast cancer through the latest contributions and findings. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are deep learning models capable of analyzing visual data, which permits top performance in any medical imaging task such as mammograms, ultrasound images, and histopathological slides. These networks can automatically identify intricate features from raw image data, thus eliminating the need for manual feature extraction, which is usually involved during conventional image analysis approaches. Studies have shown great performances of pre-trained CNN models like ResNet, Inception, and VGG in detecting and classifying tumors due mainly to the power of transfer learning [23], [24]. In addition, custom architectures of CNN for specific datasets are usually much more effective than a generic model since they capture the particular patterns or nuances relevant to breast cancer [25].

4.1 Comparative metrics of performance

The CNN-based approaches have achieved significant improvement in performance metrics such as accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity. The accuracy achieved by ResNet-50 and Inception-v3 exceeded 90% on benchmark datasets like the Digital Database for Screening Mammography (DDSM) and the Breast Cancer Histopathological Database (BreakHis) [26], [27]. Therefore, one of the most critical metrics in cancer detection as it amplifies the probability of discerning malignant cases at earlier stages is related to sensitivity, which has its particular importance in this case with these models. Several issues remain, including issues of overfitting of the models for small datasets as well as different performances for different imaging modalities.

4.2 Hurdles and Till Limitations

While CNN algorithms have proved to be successful, there are several challenges in using them. One of the greatest challenges is that of labeled databases - large-sized labeled databases do not exist. Most of the publicly available databases are small in size, with most of them not originating adequate examples for different tumor types, patient varieties, and imaging modalities; the result is that CNN models cannot generalize well [28]. Further, deep CNNs are heavy on computations. Because of that, they require a lot of space and time to train and use the model. This aspect becomes a problem in resource-poor settings such as rural health care centers. Another aspect is the interpretability of CNN predictions wherein the "black-box" of deep learning models becomes a challenge for clinicians in terms of trusting their predictions fully, especially in high-critical areas like cancer diagnosis. With this concern, recently, greater attention has been paid to integrating explainable AI (XAI) methods into CNNs. These techniques aim to improve transparency and interpretability so that the model helps clinicians understand and validate predictions better [29].

5. Future Perspective

This means that tomorrow's CNN-based methods for breast cancer detection will have to forge new paths or new ideas. For instance, with techniques such as generative adversarial networks (GANs), synthetic data can add to current datasets, thus increasing the number and diversity of training data[30]. Lightweight CNN architectures and model compression algorithms are designed to implement these CNNs, even in the sparsest environments. One promising future application involves the increased utilization of multi-modal data to include imaging alongside genomics, clinic, and histology information, all of which will boost the accuracy of diagnosis. Because of this, treatment has become more personalized than ever before since it provides a more comprehensive profile of the patient's condition. Research on federated learning can be used to train CNN models on decentralized datasets while keeping data privacy-there is a lot of concern in healthcare applications about this aspect. [41]

6. Conclusion

The present study underscores the promise of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in analyzing mammograms for the purpose of early breast cancer detection. The findings suggest that CNNs can be quite useful by achieving good levels of sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy, and will be, therefore, valuable to clinical diagnostic practices. They can improve patient outcomes considerably through early detection, which would lead to timely intervention and reduction in death rates. Future work should address the limitations raised in the present study, increase the datasets, and work towards better model interpretation for the integration of such AI technologies into medical practice.

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